

ROLE OF MATRIX RESIN ON THE FLEXURAL FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF UNIDIRECTIONAL PITCH BASED CARBON FIBER LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The flexural fatigue strength of unidirectional pitch based CFRP laminates, using three types of resins with different moduli and glass transition temperatures are measured at several levels of loading rates and temperatures. As a result, the flexural fatigue strength of the CFRP laminates depends remarkably on the loading rate and temperature as well as the number of cycles to failure. The flexural fatigue strength as well as the flexural static strength is controlled by the mechanical behavior of the matrix resin which shows viscoelastic behavior. Therefore, the reciprocation law of time and temperature for the mechanical behavior of the matrix resin also holds for the flexural fatigue strength. Furthermore, the number of cycles of loading has less of an influence on flexural fatigue strength when compared with loading time.

Key words: Pitch based carbon fiber, CFRP, Laminate, Fatigue, Matrix resin, Viscoelasticity

1. INTRODUCTION

Pitch based carbon fibers have a high tensile modulus, because they are made from coal-tar pitch or petroleum pitch which have good graphitizability. Therefore, FRPs using a pitch based carbon fiber (pitch based CFRP) has come to be used as structural components of aircraft, spacecraft, etc., in which high modulus is required. However, the mechanical behavior of pitch based CFRP has not yet been fully clarified.

The mechanical behavior of FRPs depends remarkably on time and temperature, because of the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin. Therefore, it is important to investigate the influence of matrix resin on the mechanical behavior of FRP.

In this paper, the flexural fatigue strength of unidirectional pitch based CFRP laminates, using three types of resins with different moduli and glass transition temperatures are measured at several levels of loading rates and temperatures. The role of matrix resin on the flexural fatigue behavior of pitch based CFRP is discussed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1. Preparation of specimens

Pitch based unidirectional CFRP laminates, using the three types of resins with different moduli and glass transition temperatures are prepared. The carbon fiber is a pitch based carbon fiber XN40 (Nippon Oil, brand name Granoc). The matrix resins are a general purpose epoxy resin 25C, low modulus epoxy resin 25X and modified polycyanate resin RS3. Prepreg sheets (Nippon Oil) made from these resins were stacked into layers and formed into 3 mm thick unidirectional CFRP

laminates. The fiber volume fraction was approximately 55 %. In the following, these three types of unidirectional CFRP laminates are referred to as XN40/25C, XN40/25X and XN40/RS3.

2.2. Test procedures

Three point flexural fatigue tests for XN40/25C, XN40/25X and XN40/RS3 were conducted by using an electro-hydraulic servo testing machine. The thickness, width and length of all specimens are 3 mm, 10 mm and 80 mm respectively. The span is 60 mm. These specimens were loaded at two levels of temperatures with loading rates of 5 Hz and 0.05 Hz. Stress ratio (minimum stress/maximum stress) is 0.05.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The viscoelastic behavior of the three types of resins and the flexural static strength of CFRPs using these three types of resins as matrices are explained before entering the discussion on the flexural fatigue strength of these CFRPs.

3.1. Viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin

Figure 1 shows the storage moduli E' versus temperature for the three types of resins at time (frequency⁻¹) $t = 1$ min. The reciprocation law of time and temperature holds for the storage modulus. Therefore, the master curves of E' versus reduced time t' for the three types of resins at the reference temperature $T_0 = 25$ °C and the time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ can be obtained as shown in Figure 2 and 3, respectively. These storage moduli change remarkably with time and temperature not only above glass transition temperature T_g but also below T_g . Each three resins possess individual properties of glass transition temperature T_g , time-temperature dependence of storage modulus E' and activation energy ΔH .

3.2. Flexural static strength

Figure 4 shows the flexural static strengths σ_{bs} versus reduced temperature T' for the three types of CFRPs at the reference time to failure $t_{f0} = 1$ min. The reciprocation law of time and temperature holds for these strengths. Therefore, the master curves of σ_{bs} versus reduced time to failure t'_f for the three types of CFRPs at the reference temperature $T_0 = 25$ °C and the time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ can be obtained as shown in Figure 5 and 6, respectively. These flexural static strengths change remarkably with time to failure and temperature not only above glass transition temperature T_g but also below T_g .

The flexural static fracture of CFRPs is classified into three modes due to the time to failure and temperature. In the initial reduced time region, the fracture mode of each CFRPs is the tensile fracture of the surface layer on the tension side of specimen where the flexural static strength changes scarcely with time to failure and temperature. In the intermediate reduced time region, the fracture mode of each CFRPs is the compressive fracture of the surface layer on the compression side of specimen where the flexural static strength decreases suddenly with time to failure and temperature. In the final reduced time region, the fracture is triggered by the microbuckling of fiber in the surface layer on the compression side of specimen where the the flexural static strength decreases with time to failure and temperature.

The time-temperature dependence of the flexural static strengths of the three CFRPs using the three types of resins as matrices as shown in Figure 4 and 5, corresponds well with the time-temperature dependence of the storage moduli for the three types of resins as shown in Figure 1 and 2. Furthermore, each activation energy of the flexural strength of the three types of CFRPs agrees well with the correspondings activation energy of the storage moduli of the three types of resins as matrices.

3.3. Flexural fatigue strength

The flexural fatigue strength versus the number of cycles to failure N_f for the three types of CFRPs at a temperature of $T = 25$ °C and a loading rate of $f = 5$ Hz and 0.05 Hz are shown in Figure 7 and 8, respectively. The time to failure t_f is equal to N_f / f . The flexural fatigue strengths of the three types of CFRPs depend remarkably on N_f and t_f in the region of N_f below 10^4 . In the region of N_f above 10^4 , the flexural fatigue strengths for the three types of CFRPs changes scarcely with N_f and are approximately equal to each other. The time to failure dependence of the flexural fatigue strengths of

the three types of CFRPs corresponds well with the time to failure dependence in the intermediate region of the flexural static strength for these CFRPs as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 9 shows the flexural fatigue strength at the two levels of loading rates and temperatures versus the number of cycles to failure N_f for the three types of CFRPs. The flexural fatigue strengths depend remarkably on loading rate and temperature as well as N_f . The condition of temperature $T=25^\circ\text{C}$ and loading rate $f=0.05\text{ Hz}$ can be converted respectively into the conditions of $T=80^\circ\text{C}$ for XN40/25C, $T=100^\circ\text{C}$ for XN40/RS3 and $T=60^\circ\text{C}$ for XN40/25X at a loading rate of $f=5\text{ Hz}$ by using the reciprocation law of time and temperature. The time-temperature shift factors $a_{T_0}(T)$ of the flexural static strength for the three types of CFRPs as shown in Figure 6 are used for these conversions. These $a_{T_0}(T)$ below T_g can be expressed by Arrhenius' equation as follows.

$$\text{Log } a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303 G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right)$$

Where ΔH is the activation energy kJ/mol, G is the ideal gas constant $8.4 \cdot 10^{-3}\text{ kJ}/(\text{K}\cdot\text{mol})$, and T and T_0 are respectively the testing temperature and reference temperature in K.

The flexural fatigue strengths versus the number of cycles to failure N_f at a loading rate of $f=5\text{ Hz}$ and a temperature of $T=80^\circ\text{C}$ for XN40/25C, $T=100^\circ\text{C}$ for XN40/RS3 and $T=60^\circ\text{C}$ for XN40/25X agree well with those at $f=0.05\text{ Hz}$ and $T=25^\circ\text{C}$. Therefore, the reciprocation law of time and temperature for the flexural static strength of these CFRPs also hold for the flexural fatigue strength.

Figure 10 shows the flexural static and fatigue strengths for the three types of CFRPs versus time to failure t_f at a temperature of $T=25^\circ\text{C}$. The flexural fatigue fracture of XN40/25C and XN40/RS3 is classified into two modes due to the time to failure t_f . In the initial region of t_f , the fracture mode of these CFRPs is tensile fracture of the surface layer on the tension side of specimen where the flexural fatigue strength changes scarcely with t_f as well as the flexural static strength. In the final region of t_f , the fracture mode is compressive fracture of the surface layer on the compression side of specimen where the flexural fatigue strength decreases with t_f as well as the flexural static strength. The difference in flexural static and fatigue strengths at the same t_f represents the dependence on the number of cycles to failure N_f . It is clear from this figure that the number of cycles to failure N_f has less of an influence on flexural fatigue strength when compared with time to failure t_f .

4. CONCLUSION

The flexural fatigue strength of unidirectional pitch based CFRP laminates, using three types of resins with different moduli and glass transition temperatures are measured at several levels of loading rates and temperatures. As a result, the flexural fatigue strength of the CFRP laminates depends remarkably on the loading rate and temperature as well as the number of cycles to failure. The flexural fatigue strength as well as the flexural static strength is controlled by the mechanical behavior of the matrix resin which shows viscoelastic behavior. Therefore, the reciprocation law of time and temperature for the mechanical behavior of the matrix resin also holds for the flexural fatigue strength. Furthermore, the number of cycles of loading has less of an influence on flexural fatigue strength when compared with loading time.

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Figure 1. Storage moduli versus temperature at the $t=1$ min for the three types of resins

Figure 2. Master curves of the storage moduli for the three types of resins

Figure 3. Time-temperature shift factors for the three types of resins

Figure 4. Flexural static strength versus reduced temperature at the reference time to failure $t = 1$ min for the three types of CFRPs

Figure 5. Master curves of the flexural static strength for the three types of CFRPs

Figure 6. Time-temperature shift factors for the three types of CFRPs

Figure 7. Flexural fatigue strength versus the number of cycles to failure N_f for the three types of CFRPs ($f=5\text{ Hz}$)

Figure 8. Flexural fatigue strength versus the number of cycles to failure N_f for the three types of CFRPs ($f=0.05\text{ Hz}$)

Figure 9. Flexural fatigue strength at several levels of loading rates and temperatures versus the number of cycles to failure N_f for the three types of CFRPs

Figure 10. Flexural static and fatigue strengths for the three types of CFRPs versus time to failure